

ISic002992

I.Sicily inscription 002992

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2006.04

Last Change

2021-07-14 - Francesca Prado edited the text, tagged named entities and added English and Italian translation

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance

Original discovery not recorded.

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe, Museo Archeologico Regionale di Centuripe

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 20.6 cm

Width 15.6 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Ι(ησοῦς)] Χ(ριστός)
2. [χρηστά] Βασι [λῶχαῖ]ρε ἔζη [σεξῆτ]η · κ·ε · καὶ
5. [ένθακ]ατοικεῖς
7. [εἰς τ]οὺς αἰῶ [νε]ς □

Apparatus

Text after Libertini 1949

Translation (en)

Farewell worthy Basilo! You lived for 25 years and you'll live here forever.

Translation (it)

Addio, degna Basilo! Vivesti 25 anni e qui abiti nei secoli.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645342

EDR 146667

EDCS 70900398

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic002992>

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Bibliography

Libertini, G 1949. Iscrizioni Centuripine. *Siculorum Gymnasium*. 2: 91-97. At 96-97 no.3 fig.4

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